

ARIMA models in Weather Forecasting

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Figure 1: Clouds in Vienna, Austria. (Picture taken by the author)

ABSTRACT

This study discusses the application of ARIMA models in weather forecasting. A seasonal ARIMA model is fitted to four years of data measured in Vienna, Austria. The goal is to predict the daily average temperature values for a test period of ten months. The ARIMA model shows reasonable performance on the test dataset and captures the yearly seasonality well. In addition, other studies about the application of ARIMA models in weather forecasting are discussed and a brief outlook to new emerging Artificial Intelligence techniques in weather prediction is given as well.

KEYWORDS

weather forecasting, arima, time series modelling

1 INTRODUCTION

It is undeniable that the weather has a huge influence on many aspects and tasks of our daily lives. Weather forecasting is relevant in many fields, but especially in the domains of agriculture, air traffic and civil protection in terms of natural disasters [16]. Weather forecasting has been relevant ever since its beginnings in the 19th century [23]. However, only since the 1970s and 1980s numerical models are used for weather predictions [23]. One of the most commonly used statistical model for weather time series modelling is the AR(I)MA model which was introduced by George Box and Gwilym Jenkins in 1970 [5][14]. In this paper an ARIMA model is fitted to make a long-term prediction for temperature values in Vienna, Austria.

2 RELATED WORK

AR(I)MA modelling is a widely used statistical technique for time series forecasting in a variety of different research fields like economics [see for example [3],[9][19]], health [see for example [18][21]] and weather. Lai and Dzombak [14] fitted ARIMA models to predict the temperature and precipitation in Phoenix, USA and Chicago, USA and came to the conclusion that ARIMA models produce efficient and reliable forecasts usable in many applications where weather forecasting is required. ARIMA models in weather forecasting are also applied in [6] to predict the temperature and precipitation values in India as well as in [4] for the forecast of weather variables in Algerian Highlands.

3 THE AR(I)MA MODEL

ARMA models are a fusion of Autoregressive (AR) and Moving-Average (MA) models [13].

In [13] the AR-process, MA-process and ARMA-process are defined in the following ways:

AR(p)-process

$$X_t + \sum_{v=1}^p a_v X_{t-v} = e_t \quad (1)$$

for $\forall t \in \mathbb{Z}; p \in \mathbb{N}; a_1, \dots, a_p \in \mathbb{C}$ if $a_p \neq 0$ and a white noise $e = (e_t : t \in \mathbb{Z})$.

MA(q)-process

$$X_t - \sum_{\mu=1}^q b_{\mu} e_{t-\mu} = e_t \quad (2)$$

for $\forall t \in \mathbb{Z}; q \in \mathbb{N}; b_1, \dots, b_q \in \mathbb{C}$ with $b_q \neq 0$ and a white noise $e = (e_t : t \in \mathbb{Z})$.

ARMA(p,q)-process

$$X_t + \sum_{v=1}^p a_v X_{t-v} = \sum_{\mu=1}^q b_{\mu} e_{t-\mu} + e_t \quad (3)$$

for $\forall t \in \mathbb{Z}; p, q \in \mathbb{N}; a_1, \dots, a_p$ and $b_1, \dots, b_q \in \mathbb{C}$ with $a_p \neq 0$ and $b_q \neq 0$ and a white noise $e = (e_t : t \in \mathbb{Z})$.

Kreiß and Neuhaus [13] compare the AR-process with an equation of a regression. However, they [13] mention that in an AR-process the regressors are not independent, but the value of X of the current time point is dependent on the p previous values of X . Additionally, Kreiß und Neuhaus [13] state that MA-processes follow the idea that the current X value is also determined by the previous q values of e - which are also called shock values.

In [13] it is furthermore mentioned that the ARMA-model is only applicable to causal and stationary time series. As there are many time series in real-world processes which are not stationary, which means that their statistical characteristics are not constant over time and therefore the conventional ARMA-model cannot generate reliable predictions based on the past values, the ARIMA model was introduced [13]. ARIMA stands for *Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average* [13]. A model is called ARIMA model if not the original time series follows an ARMA(p,q) process but the differentiation of a certain order i of the time series fulfils the stationarity conditions [13].

4 THE DATASET

The dataset used in this study originates from the *Meteorology and Geodynamics* (in German: *Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik, ZAMG*) and is available under the Creative Commons Attribution License [8]. In this analysis the data measured at the measuring station in Wien-Donaufeld 160 m above the sea level is used. For the research purpose in this study only the columns *time* and *nd TTX* are relevant. The column *time* indicates when the value was measured, and the column *TTX* shows the temperature value measured in °C 2 metres above the ground level. The hourly temperature values are aggregated to a daily format via calculating the arithmetic average temperature value of each day. The temperature values from the 1st of January 2018 until the 31st of December 2021 are used for model training and the measured values from 1st of January 2022 until the 31st of October 2022 are used as test dataset.

5 MODEL & TEMPERATURE FORECASTS

For fitting the AR(I)MA model to the temperature data the statistical software *R* [15] is used. The preprocessing of the raw data is

done with the *R*-package *dplyr* [22].

Before fitting a model to the data, some basic characteristics of the temperature time series are revealed by decomposing it in the different components of a time series: seasonal, trend and irregular component. This is done with the *R*-function *decompose* of the package *stats* which is included in the basic version of *R* [15]. It is visible in Figure 2 that the time series shows a strong yearly seasonality and a slight trend towards lower average temperatures. The seasonality is not surprising as it can be assumed that a certain temperature schema repeats itself year after year.

As it is clear that the observed time series also has a seasonal component which should be taken into account in the AR(I)MA model, it's not a trivial task to determine the optimum p and q values for the model. Hence, the *R*-function *auto.arima* [11][10] is used which evaluates and compares models with different orders based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) [1] which is a common statistical quality measure to compare models with each other.

Figure 2: Decomposition into components of the temperature time series.

Based on the AIC an ARIMA(2,0,2)(0,1,0)[365] model is chosen. This means that an ARIMA model with an AR- and MA-order of 2 and a one-time differenced seasonal component has been determined as the best fitting model. The frequency is - as expected - 365, if rounded to full numbers.

ARIMA-Model

Figure 3: The temperature time series with the real values, predicted values and prediction interval.

Table 1: RMSE and MAE of fitted ARIMA model

	RMSE	MAE
Training	2.76 °C	1.87 °C
Test	4.53 °C	3.70 °C

The fitted model is now used to predict the average daily temperature for January to October 2022. The predictions are generated with the function *forecast* of the *R*-package with the same name [11][10]. The predictions can be seen in Figure 3. The blue line shows the predictions and the real values are displayed in red. The dark-grey shadowed area marks the 80%-prediction interval and the light-grey coloured region is the 95%-prediction interval.

6 EVALUATION

It can be seen in Figure 3 that the prediction is relatively accurate and matches the seasonal pattern of the real average temperatures well. The Root Mean Squared Errors and the Mean Absolute Errors of the model on the training and the test dataset can be seen in Table 1.

The accuracy measures show that both the performance on the training set as well as on the test set are acceptable. A Mean Absolute Error of 3.70 °C means that on average the prediction of

the model has an error of 3.70 °C compared with the real values, which is supportable for many use-cases where the prediction does not have to be extremely accurate. ARIMA models are easy to fit, interpretable and neither require much preprocessing nor extensive training times. It, however, has to be mentioned that although classical statistical approaches like the ARIMA model are still used in research for temperature forecasting like in the papers by Lai and Dzombak [14], Dimri, Ahmad and Sharif [6] or Bouznad et al. [4], the new emerging algorithms in the field of Artificial Intelligence also partly changed the techniques used for weather predictions.

7 OTHER APPROACHES

A study by Jaseena and Kovoor [12] compares several approaches for temperature forecasting and found Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approaches like in [20] and Support Vector Machines (SVM) like in [24] as best working prediction models for temperature forecasting.

De Saa and Ranathunga [16] compare ARIMA models with a Deep Learning approach on a similar task to the study presented in this paper: Temperature forecasts for 12 months based on a time series of temperature measurements. However, in the study by De Saa and Ranathunga [16] monthly instead of daily temperature values should be predicted. They [16] compared the ARIMA model to predictions from a Deep Learning model consisting of two one-dimensional convolutional layers and two LSTM layers. Looking at

the RMSE the more sophisticated model beats the classical statistical model with 1.9 to 2.42 Mean Squared Error (MSE) [16]. The potential of Deep Learning approaches in weather forecasting is also illustrated in a study by Schultz et al. [17].

Another approach, which has been discussed in detail in a study by Fathi et al. [7] is using Big Data Analytics for weather prediction tasks. Building a tool for weather prediction on top of Big Data techniques is also described in a paper by Aljawarneh and Lara [2].

8 CONCLUSION

In this paper a seasonal ARIMA model has been fitted on real-world data to forecast daily average temperature values for ten months. The fitted ARIMA model showed promising results considering its simplicity with a MAE of 3.70 °C on the test dataset. Furthermore, other works based on ARIMA weather forecasting as well as some other studies using different approaches in weather prediction like Deep Learning models or Big Data techniques were discussed briefly.

It can be summarised that although new emerging techniques in the field of Data Science offer a wide variety of possibilities for weather forecasting more traditional statistical approaches like ARIMA models are still used in the field. Despite the superiority in accuracy of more complex Artificial Intelligence models, ARIMA models still provide a simple, efficient and interpretable approach for time series weather forecasting. A further step in the research regarding this topic could be to fit rather lightweight Machine Learning models to the time series at hand and compare their performance as well as their process time with the measures of the presented ARIMA-model. Furthermore, also some external regressors could be included in the model to further improve its quality.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hirotugu Akaike. 1973. Information Theory and an Extension of the Maximum Likelihood Principle. , 267–281 pages.
- [2] Shadi Aljawarneh and Juan A. Lara. 2021. Meteorological forecasting based on big data analysis. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 9–11. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3460620.3460622>
- [3] Reem Alotaibi. 2022. ARIMA Model for Stock Market Prediction. Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3543712.3543723>
- [4] Imad-Eddine Bouznad, Enrico Guastaldi, Andrea Zirulia, Mariantonietta Brancale, Alessio Barbagli, and Djamel Bengusmia. 2020. Trend analysis and spatiotemporal prediction of precipitation, temperature, and evapotranspiration values using the ARIMA models: case of the Algerian Highlands. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences* 13 (2020), Issue 24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-020-06330-6> Published
- [5] George Box and Gwilym Jenkins. 1970. *Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control*. Holden-Day.
- [6] Tripti Dimri, Shamsahad Ahmad, and Mohammad Sharif. 2020. Time series analysis of climate variables using seasonal ARIMA approach. *Journal of Earth System Science* 129 (12 2020), Issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12040-020-01408-x>
- [7] Marzieh Fathi, Mostafa Haghi Kashani, Seyed Mahdi Jameii, and Ebrahim Mahdipour. 2022. Big Data Analytics in Weather Forecasting: A Systematic Review. , 1247–1275 pages. Issue 2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-021-09616-4>
- [8] Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik. 2022. Messstationen Stundendaten. (2022). <https://data.hub.zamg.ac.at/dataset/klima-v1-1h> <https://data.hub.zamg.ac.at/dataset/klima-v1-1h> (access: 8th November 2022).
- [9] Abdullah Ghazo. 2021. Applying the ARIMA Model to the Process of Forecasting GDP and CPI in the Jordanian Economy. *International Journal of Financial Research* 12 (1 2021), 70. Issue 3. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijfr.v12n3p70>
- [10] Rob Hyndman, George Athanasopoulos, Christoph Bergmeir, Gabriel Caceres, Leanne Chhay, Mitchell O'Hara-Wild, Fotios Petropoulos, Slava Razbash, Earo Wang, and Farah Yasmien. 2020. *forecast: Forecasting functions for time series and linear models*. R package version 8.13, <https://pkg.robjhyndman.com/forecast/>

(access: 15th November 2022).

- [11] Rob J Hyndman and Yeasmin Khandakar. 2008. Automatic time series forecasting: the forecast package for R. *Journal of Statistical Software* 26, 3 (2008), 1–22. <https://www.jstatsoft.org/article/view/v027i03>
- [12] K. U. Jaseena and Binsu C. Kooor. 2022. Deterministic weather forecasting models based on intelligent predictors: A survey. , 3393–3412 pages. Issue 6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2020.09.009>
- [13] Jens-Peter Kreiß and Georg Neuhaus. 2006. *Einführung in die Zeitreihenanalyse*. Springer.
- [14] Yuchuan Lai and David A Dzombak. 2020. Use of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Model to Forecast Near-Term Regional Temperature and Precipitation. *Weather and Forecasting* 35 (2020), 959–976. Issue 3. <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-19>
- [15] R Core Team. 2020. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/> <https://www.R-project.org/> (access: 8th November 2022).
- [16] Eranga De Saa and Lochandaka Ranathunga. 2020. Comparison between ARIMA and Deep Learning Models for Temperature Forecasting.
- [17] M. G. Schultz, C. Betancourt, B. Gong, F. Kleinert, M. Langguth, L. H. Leufen, A. Mozaffari, and S. Stadler. 2021. Can deep learning beat numerical weather prediction? Issue 2194. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0097>
- [18] Patsaraporn Somboonsak. 2019. Forecasting Dengue Fever Epidemics using ARIMA Model. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3375959.3375970>
- [19] Junying Song, Henghao Cheng, and Haolin Liu. 2022. Risk Trading Strategy: A Trading Strategy System Based on ARIMA and Iterative Risk Trading Model. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 230–236. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3537693.3537728>
- [20] Saktaya Suksri and Warangkha Kimpan. 2016. Neural Network training model for weather forecasting using Fireworks Algorithm. *2016 International Computer Science and Engineering Conference (ICSEC)*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSEC.2016.7859952>
- [21] Hiteshi Tandon, Prabhat Ranjan, Tanmoy Chakraborty, and Vandana Suhag. 2022. Coronavirus (COVID-19): ARIMA based time-series analysis to forecast near future. *Journal of Health Management* 24 (2022), 373–388. Issue 3. <https://gisanddata.maps.arcgis.com/apps/opsdashboard/index.html>
- [22] Hadley Wickham, Romain François, Lionel Henry, and Kirill Müller. 2021. *dplyr: A Grammar of Data Manipulation*. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr> R package version 1.0.7, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr> (access: 8th November 2022).
- [23] Ziniu Xiao, Bo Liu, Hua Liu, and De Zhang. 2012. Progress in climate prediction and weather forecast operations in China. *Advances in Atmospheric Sciences* 29 (9 2012), 943–957. Issue 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00376-012-1194-9>
- [24] Huihui Yu, Yingyi Chen, S. G. Hassan, and DaoLiang Li. 2016. Prediction of the temperature in a Chinese solar greenhouse based on LSSVM optimized by improved PSO. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 122 (2016), 94–102. Issue 32.

A R CODE

The analysis and model fitting process has been carried out with the R-version 4.2.2.

For the package dplyr version 8.20 has been used and for the package forecast version 1.0.10 was loaded.

```
# Import
library(dplyr)
library(forecast)

# Read the data in
weather_data_full <- read.csv(file = "/weather_date.csv")

# Split Timestamp to date and time
weather_data_full <- transform(weather_data_full,
                               date = substr(time, 1, 10))

weather_data_full <- transform(weather_data_full,
                               time = substr(time, 12, 16))
```

```

# Convert date to date-datatype
weather_data_full$date <- as.Date(weather_data_full$date,
                                  "%Y-%m-%d")

# Group by date and calculate mean
w_data_tbl <- weather_data_full %>%
  group_by(date) %>%
  summarise(mean(TTX, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  rename('avg_temp' = 'mean(TTX,
                          na.rm = TRUE)')

# Only use data from 2018-2021 for training
w_data_train <- w_data_tbl[c(1:(366+365+365+365)),]

# Convert to timeseries
w_ts <- ts(w_data_train$avg_temp, frequency = 365.25,
           start = 2018)

# Decompose
plot(decompose(w_ts))

# Use Auto Arima to find best Arima model
model = auto.arima(w_ts, ic = "aic")

# Make forecasts and plot it
frequency = 365.25
days_jan_to_october = 6*31+3*30+28

forecasts = forecast(model, h=days_jan_to_october)

new_weather_data <- w_data_tbl[c(1462:(1461+days_jan_to_october))
                                ,]
new_vals = new_weather_data$avg_temp
new_times = seq(2022,
                2022 + 1/frequency*(days_jan_to_october-1),
                by = 1/365.25)

plot(forecasts, main = "ARIMA-Model",
     ylab = "average temperature per day",
     xlab = "time")
lines(new_times, new_vals, col = "red", lwd = 2)
legend("topleft", legend = c("predicted", "real"),
     fill = c("cornflowerblue", "red"))

```